

PROTECTION OF INDIGENOUS COMMUNITIES' RIGHTS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF CUSTOMARY LAW IN INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

Indonesia is a country characterized by the diversity of indigenous legal communities that possess their own systems of values, norms, and legal institutions regulating social life, land tenure, and the management of natural resources. Although the existence and rights of indigenous peoples are constitutionally recognized under Article 18B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution, in practice the protection of these rights continues to face serious challenges. Agrarian conflicts, dispossession of customary territories, and weak state recognition of customary law indicate a gap between normative recognition and substantive protection. This situation underscores the urgency of research on the protection of indigenous peoples' rights from the perspective of customary law within Indonesia's pluralistic legal system. This research aims to analyze the position of customary law in protecting the rights of indigenous peoples, to examine the forms of protection available, and to identify structural and juridical obstacles in their implementation. The research employs normative legal research using statutory, conceptual, and doctrinal approaches, through an examination of laws and regulations, legal principles, and scholarly opinions concerning the recognition and protection of indigenous peoples. The results show that customary law functions as a living law and is effective in regulating the internal life of indigenous communities, particularly in dispute resolution and natural resource management. However, its effectiveness diminishes when confronted with state law due to inadequate harmonization, conditional recognition, and the dominance of development and investment interests. Therefore, it can be concluded that the protection of indigenous peoples' rights through customary law remains limited and requires strengthening through legal reform, regulatory harmonization, and more substantial institutional recognition within the national legal system.

Keywords: Customary Law, Indigenous Legal Communities, Legal Pluralism, Rights Protection.